

Context & Methods

1. Context and definitions

- Consolidated clays are major low-permeability barriers in subsurface applications (CO₂/H₂ storage, radioactive waste disposal).
- Their electrical response is strongly frequency-dependent because several electrochemical, interfacial and dielectric processes coexist across scales, which makes broadband electrical methods particularly relevant for monitoring the confining properties of clay barriers.
- No single setup yet covers the full mHz-GHz range on one clay sample, and SIP and dielectric-spectroscopy communities interpret overlapping mechanisms differently.**
- This review critically compares their experimental signatures and models to bridge these gaps.

Equivalent representations of the same response:

- complex electrical conductivity: $\sigma^*_{eff}(\omega)$
 - complex relative permittivity: $\epsilon^*_{r,eff}(\omega)$
- $$\sigma^*_{eff}(\omega) = i\omega\epsilon_0\epsilon^*_{r,eff}(\omega)$$

2. Three methods, two measurement principles

- Impedance-based methods** (Spectral Induced Polarization, SIP and 2-electrode impedance spectroscopy, 2-IS) treat the sample as a discrete equivalent circuit in the quasi-static regime ($\lambda \gg L$),
- Wave-propagation-based HF dielectric spectroscopy**, by contrast, probes electromagnetic wave propagation through scattering parameters $S(\omega)$.

HF dielectric spectroscopy: a) CTL setup connected to the VNA (Schmidt et al. 2026) and b) the OE-probe immersed in the sample (Bore et al. 2022).

3. Three complementary methods covering the mHz-GHz range

	4-SIP	2-IS	HF dielectric spectroscopy
Useful frequency range	mHz-10/45 kHz Low frequencies (LF)	Hz-100 MHz Intermediate frequencies (IF)	~1 MHz-10 GHz (CTL) ~50 MHz-5 GHz (OE) High frequencies (HF)
Primary measured quantity	$Z^*(\omega) \rightarrow \sigma^*(\omega)$	$Z^*(\omega) \rightarrow \epsilon^*(\omega), \sigma^*(\omega), \text{ or } M^*(\omega)$	$S(\omega) \rightarrow \epsilon^*(\omega)$
Instrument	Impedance spectrometer	Impedance spectrometer	Vector Network Analyzer (VNA)
Cell geometry	4-electrodes cylindrical cell	2-electrodes parallel-plate cell	Coaxial: transmission line (CTL) or open-ended probe (OE-probe)
Regime	Quasi-static regime	Quasi-static regime	Distributed-wave regime
Main limitations	Electrode drift and polarization; parasitic EM coupling effects	Electrode drift and polarization; parasitic EM coupling effects	Calibration limits; sample geometry effects

No single experimental setup currently covers the full mHz-GHz range on the same clay sample, leaving a residual transition window (yellow band below) constrained by instrumental limits and comparatively fewer clay studies.

4. Frequency coverage of broadband electrical studies on clays

This figure provides a non-exhaustive overview of broadband electrical studies on clays across the mHz-GHz range. LF, IF and HF methods are complementary, but fully integrated measurements on a single sample remain rare.

Experimental signatures across the broadband range

5. Experimental signatures
Studies on water-bearing clays report relaxation signatures spanning the entire mHz-GHz range. The table below synthesizes the main mechanism families, frequency domains, terminologies and interpretations proposed across the literature.

Mechanism family	Authors	Materials	Author terminology (nomenclature)	Major disagreements / open issues	Reported frequency domain	Main interpretations proposed
Membrane polarization	Vinegar & Waxman (1984); de Lima & Sharma (1992); Mendieta et al. (2021)	Shaly sands; kaolinite, illite, montmorillonites	Membrane blockage; membrane polarization; possible membrane polarization effects	Mechanism generally inferred rather than isolated experimentally	mHz - Hz	Ion-selective blockage and electro-diffusional polarization at pore throats / aggregates; Mendieta et al. infer the mechanism indirectly from non-monotonic σ' evolution with salinity
Electrical double layer (EDL) polarization	Leroy et al. (2017, 2025); Jougnot et al. (2010); Breede et al. (2012); Okay et al. (2014); Mendieta et al. (2021); Bore et al. (2022); Connolly et al. (2019)	Na-montmorillonite suspensions; clay-rocks; clay-sand mixtures; shale cores; montmorillonite, illite-chlorite	Stern-layer polarization; electrochemical polarization; surface diffusion polarization (τ_{EDL}); electro-diffusional polarization (τ_s); pore-space polarization	Breede et al. emphasize pore-space geometry during desaturation rather than grain-size-controlled Stern-layer diffusion	Hz - kHz (extending to MHz - Hz; debated up to ~MHz, Revil 2013)	Counterion diffusion/electromigration within interacting clay EDLs; tangential diffusion along clay surfaces and tactoids; stronger responses associated with higher SSA and CEC
Grain polarization	Cadène et al. (2006); Rotenberg et al. (2005); Saltas et al. (2008)	Compacted smectites; Na-montmorillonite; compacted bentonite	Grain polarization (R1); grain polarization (HN-M2)	Possible overlap with EDL/Stern-layer (unresolved)	Hz - kHz	Ionic density inhomogeneity and ionic migration along clay particles producing water-content-dependent induced dipoles
Residual distributed LF contribution	Loewer et al. (2017); Schmidt et al. (2026)	Clay-bearing loess, lateritic soils, kaolin, illite, bentonites	Distributed LF interfacial relaxation processes (P3, and the debated P4); β dielectric relaxation	Contribution aggregates several unresolved LF processes	kHz toward lower frequencies (up to the lower edge of the MHz range)	Effective phenomenological contribution representing unresolved interfacial and EDL-related polarization processes
Maxwell-Wagner polarization	de Lima & Sharma (1992); Jougnot et al. (2010); Mendieta et al. (2021); Connolly et al. (2019); Bore et al. (2022); Revil (2013)	Shaly sands; partially saturated clay-rocks and shales; montmorillonite, illite-chlorite	Generalized Maxwell-Wagner polarization; Maxwell-Wagner polarization (τ_{MW}); Maxwell-Wagner relaxation	MW processes often overlap with EDL-related contributions; Revil (2013) questions MW dominance in the 10 kHz-10 MHz range	kHz - MHz (debated extension into the ~10-100 MHz range)	Interfacial charge accumulation at boundaries between phases with contrasting conductivity and permittivity: primarily the clay solid / pore-water interface, and more broadly between aggregates, pore domains and air; enhanced by multiphase heterogeneity and partial saturation.
Bound-water and counter-ion relaxation	Ishida et al. (2000); Rotenberg et al. (2005); Cadène et al. (2006); Wagner et al. (2013); Saltas et al. (2008); Loewer et al. (2017); Bore et al. (2021, 2022); Schmidt et al. (2026)	Kaolinite, montmorillonite, smectites, bentonites, clay-rich soils, loess, lateritic soils	Intermediate process ("m"); interlayer ionic dynamics (R2-R3); bound-water relaxations (R2-R4, HN-M3); P2/ τ_b ; α' dielectric relaxation	Several studies state that bound water, counter-ion and MW contributions cannot be clearly separated	MHz - hundreds of MHz (occasionally extending down to ~100 kHz, Saltas et al. 2008)	Confined/bound-water dynamics and interlayer ion motion; adsorption/desorption exchange processes; attribution remains partly uncertain in several studies
Free-water relaxation	Ishida et al. (2000); Cadène et al. (2006); Wagner et al. (2013); Loewer et al. (2017); Rotenberg et al. (2005); Bore et al. (2022); Schmidt et al. (2026)	Kaolinite, montmorillonite, smectites, bentonites, clay-rich soils, loess	High-frequency process ("h"); free-water dipolar relaxation (R5); bulk-water relaxation (R4); P1/ τ_f ; α dielectric relaxation	HF relaxation only partially resolved in some broadband studies	GHz	Dipolar relaxation of free/bulk water molecules; HF relaxation only partially resolved in some broadband studies

¹"Grain polarization" is retained as the original terminology used by Cadène et al. (2006) and Saltas et al. (2008). Although it involves tangential ionic motion along clay particles and may partially overlap conceptually with EDL/Stern-layer polarization, the cited studies do not formally identify both mechanisms as equivalent.

Reported frequency ranges for each mechanism overlap strongly across studies, because the clay response depends on sample properties: mineralogy, salinity, saturation, water content, microstructure, as much as on the mechanism itself.

The same relaxation may therefore appear at different frequencies between datasets, as shown below for salinity, temperature and clay type.

6. LF vs HF models

LF SIP and HF dielectric models often rely on similar Cole-Cole-type mathematical structures but assign different physical meanings to fitted parameters. The table below compares the main modeling families used across the broadband range.

	LF (SIP, mHz-kHz)	HF (Dielectric, kHz-GHz)
Phenomenological models	Cole-Cole / CCM / Pelton; same Cole-Cole mathematical structure but debated τ interpretation; constant-phase formulations	GDR: superposition of Cole-Cole dielectric relaxations (α, α', β). CPCM adds a LF Cole-Cole conductivity term and bridges dielectric spectroscopy with SIP
Mechanistic models	EDL/Stern-layer frameworks coupling Donnan equilibrium with Stern + diffuse layer conduction and membrane polarization; particle-scale polarization scaled up to the sample via effective-medium theory	Mechanistic interpretations proposing persistent EDL/Stern-layer polarization up to MHz frequencies (Revil 2013), questioning exclusive MW dominance; interlayer cation dynamics in smectites (Rotenberg et al. 2005)
Mixing approaches	Differential Effective Medium (DEM) theory used as a macroscopic mixing law for the complex conductivity of clay-sand mixtures and clay aggregates	ABC-M volumetric mixing framework with dispersive phase permittivities; CRIM empirical dielectric relationship commonly used as a baseline dielectric interpretation
Main physical mechanisms represented	Membrane polarization; Stern + diffuse layer polarization; LF interfacial polarization effects sometimes interpreted as Maxwell-Wagner-type processes	Free and bound water relaxation; interlayer ion dynamics; interfacial polarization; possible residual low-frequency EDL-related contributions
Main limitations / unresolved issues	Ambiguous physical interpretation of fitted τ parameters; unresolved attribution of EDL/Stern-layer contributions	~45 kHz-1 MHz transition under-studied on clays; stand-alone 2-IS datasets exist but are rarely integrated into broadband cross-domain calibration

Synthesis & Conclusion

7. Critical synthesis

Broadband clay spectra reflect overlapping polarization mechanisms with debated interpretations. The strongest overlap occurs in the intermediate kHz-MHz range, where EDL, Maxwell-Wagner and bound-water related processes may coexist.

The main conceptual divergences emerging from the literature are summarized below:

Divergent mechanism attribution	EDL-Maxwell-Wagner debate
Similar spectral features are interpreted differently depending on the framework and sample type. MW polarization is alternatively described as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> interfacial charge accumulation, conductivity/permittivity contrasts in heterogeneous media, or grain-scale capacitor networks. Intermediate-frequency relaxations often cannot be uniquely assigned (bound water vs interlayer ion dynamics vs Maxwell-Wagner effects).	Reported frequency ranges strongly overlap across studies. EDL polarization is placed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> below kHz by Mendieta et al. (2021), below ~1 kHz by Leroy et al. (2025), Revil (2013) instead proposes a broadband Stern-layer dominated framework with limited Maxwell-Wagner contribution. Bore et al. (2022) report Maxwell-Wagner polarization around hundreds of kHz and exclude it from their conductivity model ($f_{MW} \approx 70$ kHz, Leroy et al. 2017). The dominant mechanism across the kHz-MHz transition range remains actively debated.

Inconsistent nomenclature across communities

- Dielectric spectroscopy:
- α = free-water relaxation
 - α' = bound-water / counter-ion relaxation
 - β = residual LF contribution
- Electrochemical terminology (Revil 2013):
- α = EDL polarization
 - β = Maxwell-Wagner polarization
 - γ = free-water relaxation
- Mechanism-based terminology is therefore preferred in this synthesis.

Petrophysical modulation

Relaxation amplitudes and frequencies depend strongly on:

- cation exchange capacity (CEC),
- specific surface area (SSA),
- salinity,
- water content,
- swelling behavior,
- compaction / porosity

Swelling clays exhibit:

- stronger LF σ'' responses,
- stronger MHz-range polarizability.

High salinity may reduce membrane-related polarization through diffuse-layer compression and coagulation.

Toward a unified interfacial framework

Several LF polarization mechanisms reported across the literature may partially reflect related EDL-controlled interfacial processes acting across scales. The negative surface charge of clay minerals promotes counter-ion accumulation within Stern and diffuse layers, whose motion contributes to conduction and polarization. Depending on the conceptual framework and spatial scale considered, these effects may be described as EDL, membrane, grain or interfacial polarization.

8. Perspectives and applied impact

Perspective	Targets
Experimental integration	Develop integrated broadband setups on a single sample, covering the single-sample frequency window between 4-electrode SIP and HF dielectric spectroscopy that remains poorly resolved in clay
Microstructure - spectra relationships	Relate broadband relaxation signatures to clay microstructure (particle/aggregate organization, interlayer geometry, swelling state and pore structure).
Unified modelling	Extend mechanistic EDL models toward HF and integrate bound-water effects into LF frameworks

Better broadband understanding → improved non-intrusive monitoring of clay confining properties for CO₂, H₂ and radioactive waste storage.

QR code: full bibliography and glossary
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